

The challenge: Searching for Research on Red AI, the Environmental Impacts of Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

We report this case to serve dual ends. First, we share our lessons learned to inform how others might investigate Red AI, a term for the environmental impact of artificial intelligence drawn from a seminal paper on this topic (Schwartz *et al.*, 2020).¹ Second, we seek to raise awareness of the complexities and trade-offs in “tech mining” certain research domains. Novel to us was the degree to which the target in this case confounded with other literature, necessitating human screening of many papers (abstract records) to determine suitability for inclusion in the study data set. We report a mixed data sampling approach and a multifaceted, iterative search refined over more than two years that does not lend itself to straightforward replication.

1. Introduction

The research addressed in this paper arose from multiple motivations. One was to understand the scope and pattern of research on the environmental impacts of artificial intelligence (AI). As part of a larger effort of the Network for the Digital Economy and the Environment (nDEE, <https://www.NetworkDEE.org>) to identify research gaps, the focus is largely on negative environmental impacts. Research on beneficial uses of AI is extensive and less in need of such analysis (Schoormann *et al.*, 2023). This paper focuses on the challenges in assembling a suitable Red AI dataset for research profiling, only briefly noting our preliminary findings on research patterns.

The study plan was to assemble a dataset of papers in the form of abstract records gathered via searching in publicly accessible data repositories, such as Web of Science (WoS). Then, bibliometric and text analytic methods (“tech mining” -- Porter and Cunningham, 2004) would be employed to identify leading researchers and institutions, focal topics, the journals where such research is published, and patterns and evolution of such research over time.

¹ In contrast to Red AI, Schwartz *et al.* (2020) use the term “green AI” to refer to “AI research that is more environmentally friendly and inclusive.”

In our experience, some research domains have a sharply defined topic, reflecting a tightly interconnected research community that shares core terminology, c.f., dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) (Guo *et al.*, 2012). Other research domains are huge, with evolving terminology, posing challenges for searchers. For bibliometric analyses on nanotechnology, multifaceted and evolving terminology posed challenges, but human review of each abstract was not required, nor would it be feasible with over a million records accruing (Arora *et al.*, 2013).

Recently, “Long COVID” presented search challenges. In this case, use of the standard National Library of Medicine (NLM) LongCOVID search query in Medline, through the PubMed website, was compared to another group’s compound query (Gehanno *et al.*, 2024). At first, both searches retrieved about 28,000 papers (abstract records). However, only about 20,000 were in common. Given the murky nature of LongCOVID symptoms and bounds—and, hence—research descriptor variance, this is not shocking. But search set differences do complicate comparing analyses and drawing conclusions.

Here, for Red AI, we describe devising a search strategy for a research domain that presents a complex of challenges, including:

- Diverse research disciplines with different emphases and publishing norms; we key on computer science (CS) vs. non-CS.
- The prime mover, AI, in this study, involves different components, with differing degrees of technical specification (e.g., “FPGA”—field programmable gate arrays; machine learning, training).
- Intent to distinguish intersecting, but contrasting in important ways, research on AI as a cause of environmental impacts vs. AI as a remedy for particular impacts. One might strive to separate this Red AI vs. Green AI, confronting extensive overlap in terms used in both research endeavors. Those difficulties point to human review of each abstract record essential to determine suitability for inclusion in the dataset that we label Red AI. However, human review is resource-intensive and subjective.

This paper describes challenges in obtaining a viable Red AI dataset and implications for such STI analyses.

2. The Data Journey

2.1. Challenges in Search Formulation. Unlike the typical STI paper that straightforwardly describes the data source(s) and procedures to search and retrieve the pertinent data, we herein describe several challenges in generating a suitable dataset to study Red AI.

To begin, there are difficulties in scoping what topics to include in a study of Red AI. The most prominent concern in Red AI research is the energy load of AI “compute,” i.e., the sometimes very large energy consumption to train and then apply large language models, deep machine learning, etc. Another perspective comes from very broad concerns about AI’s contribution to sustainability and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), rebound effects, misleading output from AIs used in environmental science and management, or generation of e-waste management. A recent report by the OECD (2022) on environmental impacts of AI emphasizes the need to expand the scope of environmental concerns beyond energy and climate.

To get a sense of the scope of potential Red AI concerns, Wu *et al.* (2022) present a systems perspective on AI energy consumption, drawing heavily on Facebook’s experiences. Carbon footprints are generated in obtaining and treating data; devising, training, and running

algorithms; and embodiment in compute hardware.² Training large language models can pose a heavy load, but so can running such models. They also point out that ever-increasing data volume has driven a super-linear trend in model size growth; hence, heavier energy loads. Such energy loads can get large, as they cite an example of training one large machine learning model being comparable to driving a car some 240,000 miles. To the good, providing low carbon energy can reduce the growing climate impacts from the use of AI. They also report Facebook making gains in carbon footprint reduction. One part of their call for action to reduce AI energy loads concerns the “edge,” i.e., uses on equipment and devices away from central data centers. They urge development of sustainability metrics.

AI contributes to a wide array of computing systems and diverse applications. Certainly, many of those entail a mix of “cause” and “cure” possibilities for environmental impacts. It proved difficult for us to draw the line between what constitutes AI vs. broader systems to which AI contributes. In formulating our searches, we considered whether to include robots, drones, and the Internet of Things (IoT) as AI (exploring possibilities with and without them). Smart city development and rebound effects (wherein increased efficiency from the use of AI leads to increase in energy consumption) pose categorization challenges also.

In sum, we were not able to devise Boolean search formulations that captured research on Red AI issues without also retrieving extensive research on ways that AI helps resolve environmental issues. Combining such term-based searching with additional information—such as Web of Science Categories (WoSCs)—did not resolve this issue.

That pointed our research team to manual review to assess which records warranted inclusion. Criteria for inclusion were hard to fashion. To what extent a paper³ addressed Red AI was highly variable, and how to measure that was challenging. The sharpest focus might have been to restrict to papers on AI compute energy load, but we sought a broader swath of possible environmental impacts. We discussed criteria to improve rater consistency, but we did not allocate resources for multi-rater reviewing.

2.2. A Composite, Iterative Search Approach. We combined multiple search approaches, iterating over time. We searched variously in WoS, Scopus and arXiv; later consolidating to analyze only records in WoS. Figure 1 presents an overview of our search and refinement processes (extending from January 2022 to August 2024) in our hunt for Red AI research.

Multiple Boolean searches were adapted from variously combining three components:

- a) AI, mainly using an 8-term query, yielding ~775,000 WoS records⁴
- b) Environmental or social factors, a 30-term version yielding some 2,100,000 WoS records⁵

² Energy footprint breaks out at AI Facebook roughly: 31% on Data; 29% for Experimentation/Training, and 40% for Inference (running the models).

³ We use abstract records; very occasionally did we read full papers.

⁴ Here is an example without robots and drones applied in WoS: (TS = ("Artificial Intelligen*" or "Machine* Learning" or "machine-learn*" or "Deep Learning" or "Intelligent Agent*" or "Expert system*" or "Machine intel*")).

⁵ To give the flavor of the searching, here is one environmental/social term set used in Scopus (in conjunction with occurrence of an AI term): TITLE-ABS("Green AI" or "Green artificial intelligence" or "sustainable AI" or "Sustainable artificial intelligence" or "energy efficien*" or "power efficien*" or "power consumption" or "energy consumption") AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"cp")) AND SUBJAREA(COMP).

c) Negative outcomes⁶

The intersection of (a) AND (b) gave 27,000 records⁷, winnowed down to 1,793 for human review by ourselves and helpful colleagues.

Figure 1. Searching and Refining Red AI Research

Search routines that we performed include:

- Boolean searches using *proximity delimiters*, e.g., “NEAR/4” in WoS to more closely associate negative impact terms to AI facets. (See Footnote 6.)
- Running term-occurring searches conditional on appearance in *select journals or conferences*. Based on review by librarians and AI researchers, we added relevant conference papers (especially to capture CS research).
- Use of *Web of Science Categories (WoSCs)*, in conjunction with terms, to target environmental and social sciences⁸ treatment of Red AI.
- *Snowballing*, i.e., identifying and retrieving papers cited by a seminal paper or set of papers; also, identifying papers that cite such seminal paper(s), thus providing multiple foci/seeds). We chose the Schwartz et al. (2020) and Verdecchia et al. (2023) papers as two such seeds.

⁶ One example: AI near/4 issues terms: (((false or bias* or “side effect\$” or “negative effect\$” or risk* or damage* or danger* or harm* or concern* or consequen* or impact* or dysfunction* or adverse or vulnerab* or “cyber attack*” or degradat* or fair* or sociat* or socio-* or justice))))).

⁷ Tallies are just illustrative; exact values varied, trending upward over the 2+ years of evolving the dataset.

⁸ E.g., variants used include: WOSC=(“engineering environmental” or “environmental sciences” or “green sustainable science technology” or “environmental studies”);

WOSC = (ethics; or philosophy; or “political science”; or law; or “social issues”; or “social science, interdisciplinary”; or “biodiversity conservation”).

- Using the terms “green AI” or “sustainable AI”⁹ in new Boolean searches. This returned a relatively high concentration of Red AI-pertinent research.
- Applying differential conditions for backward (top 25) & forward cites (cite >=4) to seek Red AI-relevant papers.
- *Augmenting searches* by keying on particular terms occurring. This yielded some additional search terms with which we experimented.
- *Application of sentiment analysis* to help distinguish negative effects.
- *Opportunistic searching of sources outside the target databases*. For example, we reviewed the nDEE reference compilation (<https://bit.ly/nDEE-bibliography>, ~1000 papers).
- *Ground-truthing (human review)*. None of the search components that we tried yielded desirably high precision; they all included a mix of Red AI caused impacts and other foci (mainly the application of AI to help reduce environmental impacts). We also removed duplicate records among search components.

2.3. *Accepting Bias*. We tolerated unequal sampling to allow us to overweight records in the far less populous non-CS publications. The candidate Red AI research literature is dominated by CS—on the order of 4X as large as the non-CS papers set that we identified. Our resources were too limited to do manual review of a full set of 2,899 CS papers retrieved, so we drew a random sample of 500 of those (some 17%)¹⁰. On the other hand, we assessed each reasonable candidate Red AI non-CS paper retrieved. We thus traded off comprehensiveness and representative sampling in favor of relative over-weighting of non-CS research. That allowed us to identify less frequent topics addressed in the non-CS literature.

We caution that our data analyses are aimed toward discovery of Red AI issues being treated in the extant research, but not unbiased representation of the body of research. This requires caution in interpreting topical emphases, research community make-up, and trends for which emphases differ between Red AI research in CS vs. non-CS literatures. We note that attendant data extension, such as citation-based snowballing, is also not unbiased, in that CS and non-CS citation concentrations and norms differ. We traded these limitations in favor of identifying a wider spectrum of Red AI issues and research approaches than we could have attained with fully representative data sampling.

We determined to extend the Red AI dataset beyond the 323 records generated as of late 2023 by the steps in Section 2.3. We set aside concerns about representativeness in favor of identifying additional Red AI research (enhancing recall). This was done primarily by means of snowballing indicated as “Additional search methods” in Figure 1.

2.4. *Human Judgment*. A driver of the difficult choices of Section 2.3 is our determination that human assessment (ground-truthing) of the suitability of individual abstract records for inclusion in the Red AI dataset considerably reduced the noise therein (see Section 2.1 too).

3. Select Results

As noted, this paper presents our issues and search approaches in studying Red AI. Here we mention just a few preliminary analytical findings.

⁹ We also used “artificial intelligence” in such formulations.

¹⁰ The dataset also includes CS papers obtained via other search elements (hence, Figure 1 suggests an approximate 25% sampling).

Recognizing our uneven sampling that under-represents CS work on Red AI, we are nonetheless able to note that the CS and other research literatures addressing Red AI issues are relatively separate. Cross-citation between those communities was relatively uncommon. Some non-CS papers cite a few prominent CS papers. CS citation of non-CS research was largely limited to papers in especially high profile, multidisciplinary journals, such as *Science*.

Figure 2 shows papers organized by disciplinary-oriented groups (columns) and topic categories (rows). Even though, as noted, we sampled the papers published in CS literature (conferences; journal articles), nonetheless, the 600 Red AI related papers are most heavily found in CS outlets. So, were one searching for environmental issues in the application of AI (“inference”), Figure 2 suggests most are to be found in CS literatures. Also, most papers that we found to treat quantification are mainly in CS literature, but typically reporting results of tests of new software methods and hardware rather than comprehensive calculation of life cycle-wide impacts. Conversely, were one pursuing ethical issues, the social and environmental literatures are well-represented; so also are the “CS + Other” literatures (i.e., papers in journals or conferences that WoS categorizes in both CS and Other disciplines).

Figure 2: Select "Red A" Research Topics by Disciplinary Groups						
# Records		474	183	49	30	10
	Topic Categories \ Disciplinary Groups	Computer Science (CS)	CS + Other	Environmental	Social	Multi-disciplinary Sciences
98	Inference (Applications)	92	23	4	0	1
92	Quantificaion	83	19	3	1	1
58	CS (no mention of energy)	58	7	0	0	0
24	Ethics	7	16	6	9	1
10	Urban	7	5	2	2	0

Again, recognizing our partial sampling of CS research, we identify some terms of potential interest being used in the papers in the five disciplinary groups in Figure 2 and offer observations on coverage:

- Both training of AI (e.g., developing large language models) and AI applications (inference) warrant research attention.
- More technical sub-topics, not surprisingly, are to be found largely in CS literature. E.g., 44 abstract records mentioning “convolutional neural networks” are all in CS-related literature.
- Also, unsurprisingly, energy issues dominate in our 600 Red AI records—the term “energy” appears in 382 of them (64%).
- Energy consumption is predominantly addressed in CS papers. Interestingly, papers in CS+Other (i.e., in journals or conferences categorized in both CS and other WoSCs) heavily mention “carbon footprint,” but not energy consumption.
- Some terms relatively concentrating in environmental and social science papers include: development, sustainability, impact, climate change, and carbon emissions—but the numbers are small, as we have only 49 papers published in environmental WoSCs and 30 in social science WoSCs.

- Some terms well-represented in both “CS+other” literatures include: development, carbon footprint, and sustainable/sustainability (proportionately, papers in environmental and social WoSCs are even more apt to mention sustainability).
- Of 24 mentions of “Ethics,” 16 are in “CS+other” literature; 9, in social science literature.

We mention a few research profiling observations at this time:

- In our dataset, the most cited authors are Emma Strubell (c.f., (Strubell, Ganesh and McCallum, 2019)) and Roy Schwartz (c.f., (Schwartz *et al.*, 2020)).
- Some 63 countries have authors on one or more of these 600 papers, led by the USA (215), China (81), UK (56) and Germany (50).
- This Red AI literature is expanding; 59% of the 600 papers date 2021 or later.

4. Conclusions

Section 3 presents a few results concerning Red AI research. We hope these inform future studies of the Red AI arena with respect to topics to consider and issues to confront in identifying pertinent research. We conclude that there are notable considerations that should be raised concerning environmental research on AI.

Our other set of conclusions bear on searching for research on one’s target STI domain. Our Red AI case illustrates challenges worthy of attention as researchers formulate search strategies, concerning:

- The formulation of the target domain and specifying criteria to distinguish what belongs in and how to operationalize this.
- Possibilities of sampling subsets of the data differently (thus biasing but gaining coverage advantages).
- Trade-offs between value-added, licensed data resources and open sources; trade-offs between limiting to a single data source and incorporating multiple sources (for richer coverage, but at the cost of data heterogeneity that could undercut analyses).
- Incorporating AI tools to help distinguish pertinent data. We had limited success with, but see potential in, sentiment analyses to characterize the nature of a study. Likewise, we see potential in knowledge modelling to go beyond exact term occurrence being required to determine study relevance; this can also extend study reach beyond a prescribed dataset (Wu *et al.*, 2023).¹¹
- Extending text analytics could enhance discernment of key study attributes. Subject-action-object analyses that use text structure (sentences) could augment distinguishing relevance (c.f., Liu, Feng and Uden, 2023).
- Use of full texts (papers) rather than abstract records with meta-data is an option. That entails high costs to acquire (but open sourcing can aid) and to process; it also introduces a higher degree of noisy information.

Future research to compare search and refinement tools presents important opportunities. As a reviewer of this paper helpfully noted, emerging tools to designate micro-topics could help sharpen focus. And, especially, AI-supported search engine capabilities (e.g., offered by Scopus) and desktop AI tools to capture “more records like this” should be compared on different search challenges. For one, semi-automating ground-truthing could help resolve our Red AI search complexities and, thereby, facilitate replication.

¹¹ We applied *VantagePoint* (www.theVantagePoint.com) auto-categorizer capabilities. The small 600 record data set limits data modeling, but such tools warrant trial with other, more extensive data domains.

Another issue warranting study is how to deal with different disciplinary publication and database norms. In this Red AI study, we grappled with CS vs. non-CS differences. Prominent is the priority of presenting research in conferences for CS, vs. publication in journals in many other fields. Scopus and Web of Science cover well-regarded journals more consistently and completely than they do conference proceedings. In addition, consolidating conference name variations in abstract records poses a challenge. *VantagePoint* usefully consolidated those, but errors remain likely. In terms of data resources, we note that open sources, such as arXiv, can enrich coverage, but issues we addressed were recognition of the status of a paper (pre-print, final version, post-print) and disentangling multiple versions of a paper. These differences can complicate and, possibly, distort scientometric studies which cross disciplines that differentially rely on distinct publishing practices.

Open science practices

To varying degrees, we considered a mix of open and licensed data resources, especially arXiv (open), and Scopus and WoS, requiring a license. To help counterbalance the complexity of our searching, we decided to limit the analyses to abstract records indexed by WoS. Data heterogeneity limits analytics and poses challenges for semi-automated computer routines to refine and analyze the data. We used proprietary software (*VantagePoint* – www.theVantagePoint.com) to perform data consolidation and cleaning routines. We took advantage of WoS data quality (e.g., excellent citation tracking) and enhanced data fields (e.g., their assignment of literature to WoSCs). While human flexibilities enable dealing with heterogeneous data, machine routines can be stymied. Use of multiple, open data resources comes with costs.

Our multifaceted search process is not directly replicable. Should one want to analyze our 600 WoS records, we can provide their WoS Accession Numbers. Alternatively, DOI's can be made available for 520 of the records.

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Author contributions

Reid Lifset led conceptualization of the study, project management, and acquisition of funding. Alan Porter led the data refinement and bibliometric analyses, collaborating with Reid. Tessa Lee worked extensively on data acquisition and processing while a graduate student at Yale.

Competing interests

Alan Porter works for Search Technology, Inc., that provides the *VantagePoint* text analysis software used. They also provide the related software, *Derwent Data Analyzer*, that Clarivate (producer of WoS) offers.

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